

Selective laser ablation of single layers from SiO₂/poly-Si superlattices for patterning of 26 % efficient IBC solar cells

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Abstract

We present a new process for the fabrication of high efficiency IBC solar cells with passivating poly-Si contacts for both polarities. Aiming at short processing times and keeping commercial adaption in mind, we use in-situ doped LPCVD (Low Pressure Chemical Vapor Deposition) poly-Si layers and perform all patterning steps with lasers. We show details on the process optimization for the laser structuring, that consists of the ablation of an SiO₂ etch barrier followed by KOH etching of the exposed poly-Si layers. There is a large process window for the laser power for the layer stack we use in our experiment. This enables the removal of an *n*⁺-type doped poly-Si layer without damaging an underlying *p*⁺-type doped poly-Si layer. A batch with p-type Si cells using this new process results in a device with efficiency of 25.5 % on 3.97 cm² large solar cells. We present an analysis of the light-*IV* parameters to disclose the dominating losses. With further optimization we demonstrate independently confirmed 26.0 % efficiency on 24.5 cm² large solar cells from n-type Si.

1. Introduction

In order to achieve highest power conversion efficiencies with single junction silicon solar cells, interdigitated back contact (IBC) solar cell designs are often applied and are well represented in the latest solar cell efficiency tables [1]. For highest efficiencies, IBC are combined with passivating contacts for both polarities, like heterojunction contact solar cells with efficiencies up to 27.3 % [2], poly-Si on oxide (POLO) -based back contact solar cells with efficiencies up to 27.0 % [1] and the combination of both technologies which reached impressive efficiencies up to 27.8 % [3].

The high efficiency potential of IBC solar cells comes at the cost of increasing process complexity compared to front and back contacted solar cells. Several methods for the damage free patterning of passivating contacts for IBC solar cells have been published, aiming to reduce process complexity and cost, including inkjet printing of doping sources [4,5], inkjet printing of poly-Si layers [6], masked ion implantation [7], or masked PECVD deposition [8]. Especially popular is laser patterning [9–14], which is often considered the most viable solution for industrial patterning.

Lasers with different wavelength and pulse durations are used for a variety of process steps in solar cell fabrication, including laser doping for selective emitters [15], cutting of half cells [16], and the formation of contact openings [17–19]. Especially short pulse laser ablation of dielectric layers has been shown to introduce very low damage to crystalline silicon solar cells [20,21]. By using short wavelengths, the penetration depth of the laser and thus the depth of the laser damage can be further reduced, enabling the ablation of dielectric coatings from ~100 nm thin poly-Si layers without damaging the underlying c-Si surface [22].

In this work we use a ultra violet (UV) ps laser for the patterning of SiO₂ etch barriers on poly-Si, which is followed by wet chemical etching for the patterning of IBC structures. In order to

pattern both polarities of our POLO² IBC solar cells, we need to selectively ablate the top SiO₂ layer of a superlattice stack consisting of multiple poly-Si and SiO₂ layers, without damaging the underlying SiO₂ layers. We investigate the structuring process on symmetrical lifetime test structures and use the developed process for the fabrication of POLO² IBC solar cells.

2. Sample preparation

Figure 1. Process flow for the fabrication of so-called POLO² IBC solar cells. a) formation of *p*-type POLO layer and growth of a SiO₂ etch barrier, b) laser structuring of the etch barrier, c) wet-chemical etching of the exposed POLO layer, d) formation of the *n*-type POLO layer and growth of a SiO₂ etch barrier, e) laser structuring of the etch barrier, f) wet-chemical etching of the exposed POLO layer and alkaline texturing, g) deposition of passivation and optical layers, h) contact opening, i) PVD deposition of Al metallization and a SiO₂ etch barrier, j) laser structuring of the etch barrier, and k) wet-chemical etching of the exposed metal layer.

Figure 1 a)-k) shows the process flow for the solar cell fabrication. For the baseline solar cell development we use round *p*-type doped Float Zone silicon wafers with 150 mm diameter and a resistivity of 1.3 Ωcm, that are annealed at a high temperature to annihilate thermally activated defects [23].

- a) On these wafers we grow a ~1.5 nm thick thermal oxide layer at 600°C, followed by LPCVD deposition of a 200 nm thick *p*-type doped poly-Si layer. The *p*-type POLO junction formation is completed with an annealing process that crystallizes the poly-Si, activates the dopants, and improves the contact to the Si wafers [7,24–27]. The annealing process further includes a wet thermal oxidation step that grows a 170 nm thick SiO₂ layer that can function as an etch barrier for the POLO junction.
- b) We then ablate parts of this SiO₂ etch barrier, using a picosecond UV laser,

- c) followed by KOH etching to remove the POLO junction in the not protected regions. The p -type POLO junction in the non-etched layers will function as the hole selective contact in the finished solar cell.
- d) After a cleaning step that does not remove the SiO_2 etch barrier, a wet chemical ozone oxide is grown [28], followed by LPCVD deposition of a 200 nm thick n^+ -type doped poly-Si layer, that similar as for the p -type POLO junction is annealed and capped with a 170 nm thick wet thermal oxide layer. The used poly-Si and SiO_2 thicknesses are not optimized yet.
- e) Also, similar as for the p^+ -type POLO junction, the formed n^+ -type POLO junction is patterned by UV laser ablation of parts of the SiO_2 layer,
- f) followed by KOH etching. In the regions of overlapping p - and n -type doped poly-Si layers, the etching step will only remove the n -type doped layer, while the underlying p -type doped layer is still protected by the first wet-thermal SiO_2 layer. The laser patterns for both steps have been designed to overlap, resulting in the formation of a trench region where POLO junctions of both polarities are etched, aiming to omit parasitic recombination from a pn -junction in poly-Si [7,29]. The front side was full area ablated and etched in both patterning steps and in the next step the front side is textured in a KOH solution.
- g) While the SiO_2 etch barrier layers are thick enough to protect the underlying POLO junctions, for the first cell run an additional PECVD (Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapour Deposition) SiN_x etch barrier was deposited on the back side as additional protection for the POLO junctions. In following cell runs (see below) no additional PECVD etch barriers were deposited, thus resulting in a textured trench. After the texturing step, the dielectric films are removed in a HF solution, the wafers are RCA cleaned and both sides of the samples are passivated with 20 nm thick ALD (Atomic Layer Deposition) AlO_x layers. The front surface further receives a double layer anti-reflection coating consisting of 40 nm PECVD SiN_x and 89 nm PECVD SiO_2 , while the rear surface receives a dielectric mirror coating consisting of 30 nm PECVD SiN_x and 200 nm PECVD SiO_2 .
- h) The PECVD layers have a second function as hydrogenation layers in a following anneal at 425°C in forming gas atmosphere. For the purpose of damage free laser contact openings, the rear SiN_x layer is deposited with a refractive index of 2.4 and features high enough absorptivity at 355 nm that it can be ablated with a UV laser without damaging underlying layers [30]. The contact openings are completed with a 1 min single-side etching step in 1 % HF to remove the AlO_x layer in the contact openings.
- i) The cells are then metallized by thermally evaporating 10 μm of Al on the rear side, followed by sputtering of a 80 nm thick SiO_2 etch barrier, both in an industrial high-throughput tool from Applied Materials.
- j) The p - and n -type fingers are defined by 355 nm ps laser ablation of the SiO_2 layer,
- k) followed by etching of the exposed Al in a H_3PO_4 / HNO_3 solution [31].

In addition, symmetric reference samples on round p -type doped Float Zone silicon wafers with 150 mm diameter and a resistivity of 200 Ωcm are fabricated for the p^+ - and n^+ -type POLO junctions, the trench region and the front side, respectively. The reference wafers undergo all solar cell processing steps, with the exception, that the laser patterning steps are either conducted on full area on both sides or skipped. Metallization is only conducted on one side of the otherwise symmetric samples.

While non-metallized symmetric reference samples can be characterized with a Sinton Instruments WCT-120 lifetime tester, process monitoring at all processing stages of patterned samples is conducted via injection dependent dynILM (dynamic Infrared Lifetime Mapping) [32]. Both methods allow the determination of the saturation current density (J_0) of doped surfaces, including poly-Si layers, using the method of Kane and Swanson [33]. Solar cells are characterized with a LOANA system from pvtools, using a black measurement chuck.

3. Damage free poly-Si patterning using selective laser ablation

For the first POLO junction patterning (Figure 1 b & c), potential laser damage would be removed by the KOH step that not only etches the poly-Si layer, but also 2-3 μm into the c-Si wafer. The more critical step in this process sequence is the second patterning step (Figure 1 e & f), that in some parts of the wafer requires the removal of one poly-Si layer, without impacting the underlying POLO junction. This superlattice structure of c-Si / interface oxide / poly-Si / SiO_2 / poly-Si / SiO_2 is also shown on the left-hand side in Figure 2. For this structuring step the topmost SiO_2 layer needs to be fully removed, without damaging the underlying SiO_2 layer, as indicated by the two stars in the figure. In case of a piercing of the underlying SiO_2 layer, both poly-Si layers could be etched in the KOH step, potentially resulting in shunts in the final solar cell.

We test the viability of the process, by ablating test areas on a symmetric reference sample that features the full superlattice structure. In this experiment the p^+ -type POLO junction was formed before the n^+ -type POLO junction, but we assume that the opposite polarity can be structured similarly. We use a 355 nm ps laser with an approximately gaussian beam with a diameter of 18 μm for the laser ablation experiment. 1 cm x 1 cm large areas are ablated using laser spots arranged in a hexagonal pattern with slight pulse overlap. The minimum power for reliable laser ablation in this experiment is determined in a pre-experiment to 0.9 μJ per pulse, and is used as the lowest power. We investigate nine more power values up to 2.0 μJ per pulse. Figure 2 shows dynILM images obtained at 0.27 Suns (corresponding to an injection level of $\sim 5 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), after laser ablation (top image in the centre) and after etching for 2 min in 80°C KOH solution (bottom image). The measurements indicate that the UV laser doesn't degrade the bulk-lifetime or passivation even for high laser powers, but after KOH etching, a slight reduction in lifetime becomes apparent for laser powers of 1.6 μJ per pulse and above, indicating that the SiO_2 etch barrier was damaged. Optical microscope images (shown on the right-hand side of Figure 2) show the overlapping spots directly after laser ablation (top image), a rough surface with etched holes after the KOH step, for samples with high laser powers, indicating that the SiO_2 etch barrier below the n -type doped poly-Si was partly damaged (middle image) and a smooth surface for low laser powers, indicating that the etching stops at the SiO_2 etch stop layer (bottom image).

The experiment shows that it is possible to achieve full area laser ablation, without negatively impacting the sample lifetime. The process window is relatively large for the chosen layer stack, since no lifetime degradation is observed for pulse energies up to 1.4 μJ per pulse, while the top oxide layer was reliably opened for pulse energies down to 0.9 μJ per pulse.

Figure 2. Left: Schematic of the p^+ -type poly-Si / SiO_2 / n^+ -type doped poly-Si / SiO_2 layer stack, including a blue star indicating where the UV laser pulses are absorbed. Centre top: dynamic Infrared Lifetime Mapping at 0.27 Suns of a wafer with this layer stack after ps UV laser ablation, black boxes indicate the lasered regions, numbers indicate the pulse energy. Centre bottom: The same after etching in a KOH solution. Right: Optical microscope images of the regions indicated in the ILM images.

4. Solar cell results

4.1 Proof of concept solar cells

In a first solar cell batch, solar cells with an active area of 2 cm x 2 cm are fabricated with this process and light- I/V measurements are performed using a shadow mask with a 3.97 cm² opening, illuminating the active area of the cell, excluding busbars.

Fehler! Ungültiger Eigenverweis auf Textmarke. shows the light- I/V and masked and unmasked J_{sc} - V_{oc} parameters of the most efficient solar cell from the first batch, together with parameters predicted by 2D Quokka 2 simulations [34] using input values determined on reference samples (n^+ -type POLO junction: 4 fA/cm², p^+ -type POLO junction: 7.5 fA/cm², gap: 1 fA/cm², front side: 3 fA/cm²). The generation profile was simulated with SUNRAYS [35] using optical properties of the films as determined by spectral ellipsometry.

Table 1. Measured and simulated solar cell Light- I/V and J_{sc} - V_{oc} parameters of the first solar cell batch, based on designated area measurements on 3.97 cm² and 1.5 Ω cm base material.

	(Pseudo) Efficiency (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	V_{oc} (mV)	R_s (Ω cm ²)	pFF (%)
Masked Light- I/V and J_{sc} - V_{oc}	25.5*	42.3*	82.8*	727.0*	0.15	84.1
Masked J_{sc} - Unmasked V_{oc}	26.3	42.3		732.0		85.1
(Unmasked) Simulation	26.7	42.5	86.0	730.4	0.07 (unit cell)	86.4

*Calibrated measurement from ISFH CaTeC.

The measured J_{sc} and V_{oc} values are in good agreement with the expectations from the device simulations, but the FF (fill factor) of the measured device is lower than expected. This difference is not related to R_s issues, but already visible in the resistance-free pseudo fill factor pFF . While a reduced pFF value can have various reasons, a likely reason is recombination in the non-illuminated perimeter region of the solar cells [22,36,37].

Assuming that carrier recombination in the dark perimeter region of the solar cell could contribute to the pFF degradation, another J_{sc} - V_{oc} measurement is performed, where we measure J_{sc} values with the shadow masked solar cells and V_{oc} without a shadow mask. The measurement results are shown in Table 1. For this measurement, the carrier diffusion into the perimeter region can be assumed to be negligible under V_{oc} conditions, since the optics and passivation of the cell's perimeter area are similar to the cell area. The resulting pFF of 85.1% indicates that 1%_{abs} are lost due to recombination in the perimeter region, in addition to a voltage drop of 5 mV.

The origin of the significant gap of more than 1%_{abs} to the pFF of the Quokka 2 simulations is unclear. The full area references for textured front side, p^+ - and n^+ -type POLO junctions and the gap region all show high lifetimes and $ipFF$ (implied pseudo FF) values above 86%, and while not measured in this experiment, the 1.3 Ω cm p -type FZ cell wafers typically exhibit high Shockley Read Hall lifetimes and are limited by Auger recombination after comparable solar cell processing steps.

4.2 Improved solar cells

Aiming at improving the device efficiency in a second solar cell batch, we follow the same fabrication sequence, but employ small modifications.

By carefully optimizing the annealing process, we decrease the J_0 value of the p^+ -type POLO region from 7.5 fA/cm^2 to 6 fA/cm^2 , which is still about twice as high as we are typically able to achieve and will be further optimized in the future. A further change, not intended to improve the performance, is the omission of the additional etch barrier for the texturing step, mentioned in section 2, resulting in the texturing of the gap region including a $\sim 8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ deep etch into the Si wafer. We further aim to reduce perimeter recombination by increasing the distance between neighboring cells on our wafers, since metallized cells provide a conductive path for minority charge carriers. With these changes, the solar cell V_{OC} slightly increases by 1.5 mV and the pFF increases by 0.8 \%_{abs} (see Table 2)

Table 2. Measured solar cell Light-IV and J_{sc} - V_{oc} parameters for the second solar cell batch.

	Designated area (cm ²)	Wafer resistivity (Ωcm)	Efficiency (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	V_{oc} (mV)	R_s (Ωcm^2)	pFF (%)
First cell batch	3.97	1.3 (p)	25.5*	42.3*	82.8*	727.0*	0.15	84.1
Improved cell	3.97	1.3 (p)	25.7	41.9	84.2	728.5	0.11	84.9
Larger area	24.5	1.3 (p)	25.6	42.2	82.7	731.8	0.45	85.1
Lowly doped wafer	24.5	200 (p)	25.8	43.0	82.1	730.4	0.57	85.1
Swapped polarity	24.5	500 (n)	26.0 ⁺	42.6 ⁺	83.0 ⁺	734.5 ⁺	0.52	85.7

*Calibrated measurement by ISFH CalTec. ⁺Independently confirmed by ISFH CalTec.

By increasing the active area of the solar cells from $2 \text{ cm} \times 2 \text{ cm}$ to $5 \text{ cm} \times 4.9 \text{ cm}$, we aim to reduce perimeter recombination and indeed increase V_{OC} by another 3.3 mV and the pFF by 0.2 \%_{abs} . At the same time, we increase the series resistance of the much longer metal fingers and thereby reduce the FF to 82.7 \% , resulting in a similar efficiencies for the two cell sizes. We further fabricate solar cells on lowly doped wafers. While we found in our previous work [37] that solar cells on lowly doped wafers are much more affected by perimeter recombination and therefore perform worse than cells on $1.3 \text{ }\Omega\text{cm}$ wafers, in this work we show that by increasing the solar cell size and therefore decreasing the perimeter fraction, we are able to utilize the better J_{sc} of the lowly doped wafers [38] without suffering as much from pFF degradation, resulting in a solar cell efficiency of 25.8 \% . Using lowly doped n -type wafers, we increase the device efficiency to 26.0 \% . For this n -type solar cell we change the passivation of the perimeter region from p^+ -type doped poly-Si to n^+ -type doped poly-Si, which results in a reduced recombination in the perimeter region, that together with a reduced mobility of holes compared to electrons results in a further reduction of the perimeter recombination, and a high pFF of 85.7% .

5. Estimation of efficiency potential and discussion

While all $5 \text{ cm} \times 4.9 \text{ cm}$ -large solar cells show an improved pFF due to the smaller perimeter fraction compared to the $2 \text{ cm} \times 2 \text{ cm}$ large solar cells, the larger cells in this study suffer from increased series resistance in the 4.9 cm long metal fingers. By increasing the Al thickness from $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to $25 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, or alternatively using more busbars and thus shortening the finger length

we expect to reduce the series resistance to $0.2 \Omega\text{cm}^2$, making possible solar cells with efficiencies of 26.2 % without further changes to the process flow.

For calculating the efficiency potential of an optimized solar cell without perimeter recombination, we use the above established Quokka 2 model and replace the electrical input parameters with optimized values that have previously been achieved in our lab: J_0 of n-type and p-type POLO junctions: 1 and 3 fA/cm², respectively, J_0 of the textured and AlO_x/SiN_x passivated trench and front side: 3 fA/cm². Table 3 shows the *JV* parameters of the simulated solar cells. On 1.3 Ωcm p-type wafers, the optimized POLO junctions would increase the simulated efficiency to 27.0 % due to increases in V_{oc} and *FF* (*pFF*), respectively. On 500 Ωcm n-type wafers the simulated efficiency would further increase to 27.2 %, due to an increase in J_{sc} and V_{oc} .

Table 3. Simulated Light-IV and J_{sc} - V_{oc} parameters for solar cells in this work and ones with optimized POLO junctions.

J_0 values	Wafer resistivity (Ωcm)	Efficiency (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	<i>FF</i> (%)	V_{oc} (mV)	R_s (Ωcm^2)	<i>pFF</i> (%)
This work	1.3 (p)	26.7	42.5	86.0	730.4	0.07	86.4
Optimized	1.3 (p)	27.0	42.5	86.4	734.0	0.07	86.9
Optimized	500 (n)	27.2	42.7	86.4	738.1	0.12	87.0

These projected values are consistent to the experimental values already achieved by LONGi on large area (in our notation) “POLO² IBC” cells without shaded perimeter regions [39], in particular with respect to their efficiency of 27.03 %. Also the other IV parameters are comparable while slight deviations may result from differences in wafer thickness and doping (counteracting for V_{oc} and J_{sc}), metallization layout etc.. A comparison to the current world record for Si of 27.81 % - also achieved by LONGi but on hybrid IBC cells with an electron-collecting POLO and a hole-collecting low-temperature hydrogen-rich amorphous (nanocrystalline)-Si/c-Si heterojunction - is challenging until further details are published. We can only speculate that the difference in cell efficiency (in our case projected, in LONGi’s case experimentally achieved) is partially caused by the better passivation quality of LONGi’s hole-selective contact. Previously, LONGi reported a J_0 of 0.5 fA/cm² for this junction [40], while our best hole-collecting POLO junction exhibited 3 fA/cm² [41]. However, this difference is not sufficient to explain the full efficiency gap (our simulations would then result in an efficiency of 27.3 %). There might also be further room for improvement for the passivation quality of p-type POLO junctions since even J_0 values down to 1 fA/cm² have already been reported for a firing-based hydrogenation scheme [42].

We also acknowledge the successful demonstration of a benefit of a hierarchical texture [43–45] in the recent work from LONGi [39]. This concept improves the optics on the front side and in the gap regions on the rear, and might also be implementable into our cell fabrication process by various methods. Furthermore, we acknowledge the finding of Fong et al. [46] that the passivation quality of POLO junctions is maintained when reducing the poly-Si layer thickness down to 2.7 nm. With such thin poly-Si layers, the free carrier absorption in the poly-Si could be reduced by 1.64 mA/cm² according to our area-weighted SUNRAYS raytracing simulations with our n, k -data. Since the larger part of this long wavelength light would leave the solar cell and only a fraction would be absorbed in the c-Si absorber, J_{sc} would only increase by 0.31 mA/cm². Our first experimental attempts to implement such thin poly-Si layer into our laser-structured cell fabrication process indicate that a strong adaptation of the laser process is required. We therefore hesitate to include these possible J_{sc} improvements into our projections until future works have shown how much the process window can be extended towards thinner poly-Si layers.

6. Conclusions

We have shown a new laser-based process for the damage free structuring of passivating contacts and have demonstrated selective laser ablation of single layers from SiO₂/poly-Si superlattices. A simple process flow for the fabrication of POLO² solar cells was presented, including the LPCVD deposition of in-situ doped poly-Si layers and structuring only using laser processes. With this process flow we were able to fabricate high efficiency solar cells that after applying mitigation measures against perimeter recombination achieved an independently confirmed champion efficiency of 26.0%. We estimate a unit cell efficiency potential of 27.2 % for a solar cell with optimized POLO junctions.

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